

Reinforcing Learner Autonomy for Enhancing English Language Skills

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The fundamental purpose of education is to develop among individuals the ability to make their own decisions about what they think and do. The new emphasis on learning must be on the process of learning with the acquisition of content rather than the transmission of content. It is a term used to describe an approach to educational practice, a way of conducting courses which emphasizes student independence and responsibility for decision making. The characteristics of an autonomous language learner represent high motivation, strong curiosity, being aware of using technology, having high self-confidence. The work-cycle of an autonomous classroom is plan, execute, evaluate, and reflection. The teacher's role in an autonomous class consists as a facilitator, as a motivator and as the resource person and responsibility for creating a good environment for an autonomous class. The present paper aims to illustrate how the learner autonomy approach helps students to become independent learners for their life time.

Keywords

Autonomy, approach, learning, assessment, strategies, resources, reflection, etc.

Introduction

Traditional education has historically aimed to produce knowledgeable individuals, often framed within the concept of socialization. This approach imparted concepts, values, and skills necessary for functioning within society's current context. However, there's a shift in the perceived purpose of education towards fostering autonomous, lifelong learners.

Today's generation faces the reality that many seeking higher education have primarily learned how to learn through structured teaching methods. They often lack the ability to identify their learning needs, set objectives, access diverse resources, plan strategies independently, self-assess, and validate their assessments. Consequently, higher education programs urgently need to pivot towards nurturing autonomous and self-directed learning skills.

This new emphasis prioritizes the learning process over the mere transmission of content. It necessitates a redefinition of the educator's role from being a transmitter and controller of information to becoming a facilitator and resource for self-directed learners. However, implementing such a trans-formative shift can be daunting for educators unfamiliar with this approach. For successful implementation, teachers must understand the research-based rationale behind autonomous learning, its proven benefits, and the specific guidelines and techniques available for its application. This approach is described by various terms such as independent study, self-directed learning, student-initiated learning, and project-oriented learning.

The concept of autonomy encompasses three key dimensions: Firstly, it serves as a goal in education, an ideal behavior individuals, including teachers and students, aspire to achieve, with educators aiding students in reaching this objective. Secondly, it denotes an educational approach emphasizing student independence and decision-making, reshaping how courses are conducted. Thirdly, autonomy is inherent in effective learning, as learners must be capable decision-makers in determining what and how they learn to excel beyond a narrow scope of knowledge.

The concept of autonomy can be traced back to Ancient Greece. It was concerned with self-ruling or self-governing. Dearden (1975) has given a description of the qualities which could be observed in a person who would be thought of as autonomous.

- i. Wondering and asking, with a sense of the right to ask, what the justification is for various things which it would be quite natural to take for granted.
 - ii. Refusing agreement or compliance with what others put to him when this seems critically unacceptable.
 - iii. Defining what he really wants or what is really in his interests, as distinct from what may be conventionally regarded.
 - iv. Conceiving of goals, policies, plans of his own, and forming purposes and intentions of his own independently of any pressure to do so from others.
 - v. Choosing among alternatives in ways which could exhibit that choice as the deliberate outcome of his own ideas or purposes.
 - vi. Forming his own opinion on a variety of topics that interest him.
 - vii. Governing his actions and attitudes in the light of the previous sort of activity.
- The autonomous learner has a mind of his own and acts according to it.

Chene (1983) defines autonomy as 'one's ability to be free in regard to established rules or norms, to set the goals of one's actions and judges its value'.

The main characteristics of autonomy as an approach to learning is that students take some significant responsibility for their own learning over and above responding to instruction. Such an approach involves students taking the initiative in any or all of the following:

- Identifying learning needs
- Setting goals
- Planning learning activities
- Finding resources needed for learning
- Working collaboratively with others
- Selecting learning projects
- Creating problems to tackle
- Choosing where and when they will learn
- Using teachers as guides and counsellors rather than instructors

- Opting to undertake additional non-teacher-directed work, such as learning through independent learning materials
- Determining criteria to apply to their work
- Engaging in self-assessment
- Learning outside the confines of the educational institution
- Deciding when learning is complete.
- Reflecting on their learning process

Research Design

This study utilizes the questionnaire method to gather data. The research comprises sixty (60) recent under-graduate students from the Electronics and Communication Engineering (ECE) department at Bapatla Engineering College. Of these respondents, 30 are male students, and the remaining are female students. The survey included five statements aimed at gauging their perceptions of fundamental characteristics associated with autonomous learning practices.

Additionally, an informal interview was conducted to delve into their perspectives on improving basic English language skills through the autonomous learning approach.

Findings

The findings of the study are shown in the form of graphs.

Figure: 1

Figure: 1 shows an encouraging finding emerged from the study, indicating a prevailing positive attitude among both male and female students towards

independently setting their goals. Goal setting, as delineated by Locke & Latham (2020), stands as the cornerstone of directing one's actions towards a defined outcome. This practice not only clarifies the learning trajectory for both students and educators but also significantly amplifies students' motivation and attainment levels. The efficacy of goal setting particularly thrives when objectives are meticulously defined, striking a balance between specificity and a moderate level of challenge. Notably, for high-ability students, the collaborative construction of these goals proves most efficacious.

Teachers play a pivotal role in aiding high-ability students to establish goals that appropriately match their capacities and aspirations. Haque's (2018) concept of learner autonomy aligns with this, emphasizing the significance of students assuming responsibility for their learning journey by actively selecting learning materials, methodologies, and evaluating their own progress. Empowering learners to decide on elements such as pacing, sequence, instructional mode, and study content appears pivotal. Granting learners a stake in decision-making processes regarding these dimensions not only fosters focused and purposeful learning but also augments immediate and long-term effectiveness in their educational pursuits.

Figure:2

Figure: 2 illustrates the favorable inclination of both male and female students towards collaborative learning. Collaborative learning stands as a catalyst, enhancing learner engagement with the content and fostering inquiry-driven approaches.

Within a learner-centered framework, learner autonomy emerges as a pivotal facet. Educational researchers widely acknowledge the intrinsic value of cooperative and collaborative learning in nurturing learner autonomy. This approach fundamentally revolves around the principle of consensus-building through group collaboration, extending beyond the classroom to encompass interactions within various community settings. As espoused by Panitz (1996), collaborative learning is not just a pedagogical tool but a principle guiding interpersonal engagements, thereby shaping how individuals live and interact within diverse social contexts.

Figure: 3

Figure 3 presents a noteworthy observation: a significant percentage of both male and female students strongly affirmed their ability to locate necessary resources for their learning journey. Learning, as an action-oriented process, hinges on deliberate interactions between learners, educators, and educational materials.

In pursuit of optimal instructional practices, there is a recognized endeavor to progressively shift cognitive responsibility from the teacher to the student. Fisher and Frey's (2013) instructional framework delineates this transition, advocating for a phased approach to deep learning:

a) Initial focused instruction is delivered to the entire class by the teacher.

b) Subsequent guided instruction involving differentiated content, processes, and products through targeted interactions within small groups, catering to shared instructional needs.

Consequently, it becomes evident that facilitating a diverse array of resources—ranging from tutorials to fostering environments conducive to self-organized learning groups—serves as a cornerstone for supporting autonomous learning endeavors.

Figure: 4

Figure 4 showcases the responses of both male and female students regarding their inclination towards extending learning beyond the traditional bounds of the educational institution. The positive disposition towards continued learning outside the classroom setting is notable.

Activities such as projects inherently foster independence among students, encouraging them to operate beyond direct teacher instruction, often in pairs or small groups. Thomas (2000) aptly notes that 'A growth in self-reliance is one of the many advantages of projects.' These advantages encompass the cultivation of 21st-century skills, the integration of all language modalities, the enhancement of media literacy, and the significant boost in motivation among students.

In the realm of language acquisition, social strategies play a pivotal role as language fundamentally operates within the sphere of communication. Within this task, three key strategies—Asking Questions, Cooperating with others, and Empathizing with others—are emphasized. Among these, cooperation stands out as it fosters a collaborative spirit while reducing the emphasis on competitive dynamics. Research indicates that fostering cooperative learning environments not only elevates self-esteem and confidence but also accelerates academic progress.

However, educational institutions often prioritize competition, which, although sometimes motivating, can lead to heightened anxiety and fear of failure. Redirecting learners' focus from competition towards cooperation is crucial. Empathy, an essential component of effective communication, involves understanding others' perspectives. Leveraging social strategies not only aids in cultural awareness but also facilitates a deeper understanding of others' thoughts and emotions.

Figure: 5

Figure 5 reveals a shared sentiment among both male and female students, indicating a strong disagreement with the statement: 'I would like to reflect on my learning.' Reflection stands as a pivotal process wherein students articulate the evolution of their learning, delineate changes in comprehension, and envisage its implications for future learning endeavors. It involves constructing an understanding of a given scenario, posing inquiries, experimenting, revising one's understanding, and influencing subsequent actions based on this learning cycle.

Encouraging both formal and informal reflection mechanisms is imperative in fostering autonomous learning. Informal reflection, particularly evident in individual and group discussions, serves as an effective avenue for this introspective process. Such discussions facilitate dynamic exchanges, enabling students to make personal connections and deepen their comprehension of learned concepts.

This revised version maintains the essence while providing a refined and structured presentation of the information.

Discussion

The respondents' positive perception regarding the impact of autonomous learning on enhancing English language skills and its significance for their future is evident. The findings emphasize that a majority of students are inclined toward improving their language proficiency through autonomous learning methodologies. They engage in activities such as learning new and challenging vocabulary and listening to varied pronunciations from diverse resources. Language instructors play a crucial role in fostering their students' capacity to take ownership of their learning process, employing active and personally relevant strategies both within and outside the classroom. This guidance aims not only to enhance communication skills but also to nurture independent learning, thereby assisting students in developing broader autonomy as individuals.

However, despite demonstrating an inclination toward autonomous learning, the respondents seem to lack a comprehensive understanding of the concept, potentially impacting their learning outcomes. Notably, none of them actively monitor or evaluate their learning processes. Research indicates that granting students control over course goals and content significantly enhances language learning (Little, 1991). To foster autonomous learning capacities, educators can employ various approaches encompassed within the umbrella term of learner training, including awareness-building, scaffolding, strategy training, increased social interaction, and encouragement of reflective practices.

In an autonomous classroom, emphasis shifts from the textbook to the learners themselves. Recognizing individual interests, emotional needs, as well as educational and communication requirements becomes paramount. Learning transcends mere transmission of knowledge; it's a bidirectional process, reliant on prior knowledge and experiences.

While this study supports the practice of autonomous learning to enhance English language skills, it is important to note its limitation due to a small sample size consisting of engineering graduates, limiting its generalizability. Further, a more extensive and in-depth approach involving a larger respondent pool is necessary to explore innovative methods for autonomous learning in improving English language proficiency. This study aims to guide learners in adapting their learning methodologies to align with evolving educational norms.

Conclusion

If autonomy holds the same significance as any skill, it becomes imperative for educators to actively foster conditions that nurture its growth. Assessment practices often serve as substantial hurdles in cultivating increased student responsibility. Autonomy denotes a scenario where learners exercise their own judgment and engage in independent actions throughout the learning process. A fundamental approach to cultivating autonomy lies in teaching learning strategies. Providing learners with strategy training is key to establishing a conducive environment for autonomous learning.

To facilitate an environment conducive to autonomous learning, learners require guidance in learning strategies. These strategies not only gauge a learner's progress in the target language but also afford opportunities for self-reflection post-assessment, fostering collaborative efforts among peers. Moreover, they instill a sense of accountability in learners for their progress concerning both class-oriented and personal learning objectives.

Teachers play a pivotal, albeit directive, role in nurturing learner autonomy. Their strategic involvement is essential in crafting an autonomous language classroom conducive to learners' growth.

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